

Appendix 5

Assessment of model assumptions

Model assumptions were evaluated for all fitted models. Because diagnostic patterns were consistent across predictors within each response variable and model family, we present a representative subset of diagnostics here; full diagnostics for all models are archived and available upon request.

Diversity (Hill $q = 1$) – Model performance

Predictor: Mean Annual Temperature (MAT)

Posterior Predictive Check

Model-predicted lines should resemble observed data

— Observed data — Model-predicted data

Linearity

Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Homogeneity of Variance

Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Normality of Residuals

Dots should fall along the line

Normality of Random Effects (site)

Dots should be plotted along the line

Normality of Random Effects (beta)

Dots should be plotted along the line

Diversity (Hill $q = 2$) – Diagnostics

Predictor: Precipitation Seasonality (PS)

Histogram of Residuals

Cook's Distance

Leverage (Hat Values)

DHARMA residual

QQ plot residuals

DHARMA residual vs. predicted No significant problems detected

Abundance (Negative Binomial GLMM) – Model performance

Predictor: Mean Annual Precipitation (MAP)

Posterior Predictive Check

Model-predicted intervals should include observed data points

Misspecified dispersion and zero-inflation

Observed residual variance (green) should follow predicted residual variance (blue)

Homogeneity of Variance

Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Uniformity of Residuals

Dots should fall along the line

Normality of Random Effects (Site)

Dots should be plotted along the line

Normality of Random Effects (Beta_cluster)

Dots should be plotted along the line

Abundance – DHARMa diagnostics

Predictor: Temperature Seasonality (TS)

DHARMA residual

QQ plot residuals

DHARMA residual vs. predicted Quantile deviations detected (red curves) Combined adjusted quantile test n.s.

Biomass (Gamma GLMM) – DHARMA diagnostics

Predictor: Temperature Seasonality (TS)

DHARMA residual

QQ plot residuals

DHARMA Diagnostics: Gamma GLMM for Biomass: No significant problems detected

Biomass – Model performance

Predictor: Precipitation Seasonality (PS)

Posterior Predictive Check

Model-predicted lines should resemble observed data line

Homogeneity of Variance

Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Uniformity of Residuals

Dots should fall along the line

Normality of Random Effects (Site)

Dots should be plotted along the line

Normality of Random Effects (Beta_cluster)

Dots should be plotted along the line

